

Title: Enterprise Blockchain: There is more to blockchain than cryptocurrency

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INTRODUCTION:

The world of blockchain seems to be split in to “Suits” and “Hoodies”. While Hoodies have captured the imagination of the society with cryptocurrency and ICOs, Hoodies have been hyping the potential applications of blockchain in the enterprise and demonstrating it with PoCs largely focused on FinTech. However, much of the broader potential of the blockchain technology for non-crypto remains to be discovered and exploited.

AIM:

Consider applications of blockchain technology in enterprise setting. Take a closer look at features and functions required and valued by enterprises specially for non-traditional applications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This talk will focus on applying blockchain technology to solving problems of fraud of academic credentials and professional certifications. It will discuss the technology choices we had to make when building a blockchain to satisfy rigorous requirements of national governments, academic institutions and professional education and certification organizations and how we reconciled these requirements with the blockchain ethos for eliminating non-value intermediaries and trusted third parties.

RESULTS:

To build a blockchain of academic credentials we had to evaluate a number of blockchain technologies including Bitcoin, Ethereum and Hyperledger. We evaluated these technologies from multiple technical and business dimensions including privacy, security, scalability, ease of operation and participation and acceptability to various governments and institutions.

CONCLUSIONS:

Each of the blockchain technologies we considered has strong and weak points and there is no clear winner though Ethereum and Hyperledger have significant advantage in the enterprise setting especially when applied to our use case. Hyperledger Fabric offers a lot more flexibility at the expense of complexity. We will disclose the details of implementation at the talk.

KEYWORDS:

Blockchain; Ethereum; Hyperledger; Enterprise

BIOGRAPHY:

Leon Katsnelson is a Director and CTO for IBM Strategic Partnerships and Data Science Ecosystem. He has world-wide responsibility for democratizing access to emerging technologies. He works at the IBM Canada Laboratory where he leads a team of brilliant developers and data scientists who build, help others and educate the world on the next wave of technology. Leon and his team focus on blockchain, AI and data science and cloud.